

Sharing Clinical Trial Data

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doi: [10.5281/zenodo.13860164](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13860164)

What is the sharing of Clinical Trial Data

Sharing Clinical Trial Data (CTD) is the process of making CTD available for dissemination, with the goal of increasing credibility, transparency and reusability ([Gahl et al., 2020](#)). CTD sharing has become an important topic in the field of medical research and healthcare as yearly, large amounts of clinical trials utilize funds, resources, time, and most importantly patients, to collect research data. As it is now well recognised, these data would be of greater value if they would be shared ([Piwowar et al., 2011](#)). The sharing of CTD involves making the raw data, protocols, and results of clinical trials available to other researchers, the public and/or regulatory authorities. Sharing clinical data can be placed under the umbrella of Open Research Data (ORD). The last years have brought a constant increase in the adoption of ORD policies hinged on the sharing of research data, including CTD, according to the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) ([Wilkinson et al., 2016](#)).

Why sharing Clinical Trial Data is relevant

Sharing CTD is part of a trend towards global collaboration in medical research, which, for example, showed all of its relevance during the COVID-19 pandemic ([Maxmen, 2021](#)). Although the benefits of large-scale collaboration in medical research, which by itself can be seen as part of the broader push towards Open Science, are nowadays known, the sharing of CTD has not yet reached its full potential, since data sharing rates are consistently low across medical research ([Hamilton et al., 2023](#)) and data are not requested ([Locher et al., 2023](#)).

Sharing CTD can be motivated by several reasons. First of all, sharing CTD is anticipated to enhance the value of medical research to its full potential by enabling researchers to validate claims, explore controversies, restore unpublished trials and produce new knowledge from existing datasets ([Locher et al., 2023](#)). These approaches enable reproducibility of research results with the goal of increasing transparency and credibility of science ([Gahl et al., 2020](#)). Hence, the reuse of data can accelerate scientific advancement by enabling researchers to build on existing knowledge, avoid unnecessary duplication of studies, and identify new research questions. Overall sharing CTD therefore enhances accountability in medical research, as it allows other researchers to scrutinize and validate trial results. Data sharing has the potential to reduce research misconduct and research waste ([Mansmann et al., 2023](#)). Researchers, clinicians, and consumers suggested clear recommendations on what data should be shared, when, and under what conditions, with the goal of creating a data-sharing ecosystem supporting science and patient-centered care ([Modi et al., 2023](#)). Beyond ethical and practical reasoning, researchers are motivated to share their CTD by the increased citation rate that is associated with data sharing ([Piwowar et al., 2007](#)). This potential for increased dissemination and citation shows the added value for CTD sharing. At last, CTD sharing incentives driven by journals and funding bodies as requirements for sharing of CTD are rising. Regulatory agencies and journals have started to implement policies encouraging or mandating the sharing of CTD. For example, the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE) has established a data-sharing policy requiring data sharing as a condition for publication ([Taichman et al., 2017](#)).

At the participants level, some argue that sharing CTD promotes respect for the contributions of trial participants. In other words, researchers have an obligation to share the data obtained from participants because the collected CTD can serve broader scientific purposes beyond the original study,

thereby maximizing the value of participants' contributions (Vivli, 2024). In general, participants want their data to be shared, provided that adequate privacy safeguards are in place (Mello et al., 2018).

Nevertheless, challenges and obstacles remain in the current CTD sharing procedures. Investigators routinely refuse to share raw data from their clinical research without giving a reason (Vickers, 2006). Danchev et al. (2021) demonstrated that after the ICMJE required a data sharing statement (DSS) from submissions reporting clinical trials effective July 1, 2018, only 0,6% of the declared data sets were publicly available. This recognizes the complexities stemming from commercial interests, academic competition, and other factors, while also emphasizing the advantages for both science and the public (Abbasi, 2023). For example, Miller et al. (2019) assessed data sharing policies and practices among pharmaceutical companies and reported substantial room for improvement. Abbasi (2023) further highlighted the challenges faced by medical professionals and the role of regulators and funders in enforcing compliance with clinical trial transparency. In order to overcome barriers to CTD sharing, it is necessary to coordinate a range of efforts including funding support, ethical evaluation by institutional review boards and initiatives promoting data sharing behaviors (Locher et al., 2023). Notably, a call is made for mandatory policies regarding data and code sharing by journals and regulators as well as to encourage reader input on how best to implement and refine these policies (Abbasi, 2023). The reasons for not sharing are numerous but data access is rarely denied by the platforms. It has been shown that available datasets are clearly underused (Ohmann et al., 2021). Even if open data can become a reality, shared data are useless if they are not requested (Locher et al., 2023).

How to Share Clinical Trial Data

Policies and guidelines

Regulations on health data sharing can help in devising a structured and effective way to share CTD (Locher et al., 2023; Abbasi, 2023). Policies and guidelines have been introduced on different levels, i.e. at the (inter)national or at the journal level. Since the policies are centered on the broader scope of sharing health data in general, they also apply to CTD. Here, we highlight two important policies, one international and one Swiss policy, and the next subsection focuses on CTD-specific points of interest related to these guidelines and policies.

The National Institutes of Health (NIH) of the US implemented a new Data Management and Sharing (DMS) policy, effective from January 2023 (National Institutes of Health, 2023). This policy requires researchers to share all the data that is generated with support of the NIH. While preparing new proposals to seek NIH support, researchers are required to prepare DMS plans, which demand activities such as outlining data expectations and budgets. The potential positive impact of this policy shift on clinical research in the US is illustrated by examples of successful data-sharing initiatives, such as the NIH's initiative BioLINCC. This repository enables users to search across data and tissue specimen collections, request additional information, and submit requests directly to the collections. However, the full potential of the NIH policy is yet to be realized. As Ross et al. (2023) describe, many challenges hamper current US data-sharing efforts, including low compliance with data-sharing statements in journals, varying approval rates, and opaque policies. Furthermore, key technological challenges include establishing a platform for all research types, incentivizing well-annotated datasets, ensuring adequate support for data management, and realizing the benefits of data-sharing investments. Ross et al. (2023) suggest to prioritize certain types of data, promote responsible data stewardship, and develop training curricula. This could lead to a future where every publicly funded project aims not only to accomplish research goals but also to produce data for replication and new insights, maximizing the impact of US government's scientific funding.

In Switzerland, the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) implemented their [Open Research Data](#)

(ORD) policy in 2016. The policy requires SNSF-funded researchers to store research data, share it with other researchers, and deposit it onto public repositories. In addition, stemming from an initiative of the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation, in 2021 the umbrella organisation of the Swiss higher education institutions, [Swissuniversities](#) published the national ORD [Strategy](#). The Swiss National ORD Strategy aims to promote a culture of open science, benefiting scientific advancement and the public good by making research data more accessible and usable across disciplines. For more details on regulations of general clinical data sharing in Switzerland, read our Primer '[Clinical research data sharing in Switzerland in a nutshell](#)'.

How to prepare Clinical Trial Data for sharing

Focusing on the specific case of CTD sharing, it is important to consider a number of steps before, during and after a clinical trial ([Pellen et al., 2023](#)).

An important step before data collection in a clinical trial is to ask participants for their *consent* to data sharing. Participants of clinical trials should be informed about what data will be stored, how it will be preserved, how it is likely to be used in the long-term, and how confidentiality will be protected while sharing ([Towse et al., 2020](#)). Consent could additionally include the specification of any restriction on data sharing, e.g. participants could request that their data is not used for commercial purposes.

During clinical trials, researchers can rely on various "data capture" software solutions that simplify the *collection* and *management* of CTD. Two notable examples of such software solutions are [REDCap](#) and [secuTrial](#). Both solutions are web-based, allowing access from different locations and devices, and have been developed to comply with a variety of privacy regulations. REDCap use is free for non-profit research organizations but requires installation and technical support at the level of each organization. secuTrial can be utilized entirely from a web browser, but it offers the additional option of own data hosting, i.e. of an organization-specific installation. Essentially, both tools combine the creation and distribution of surveys or data collection forms, the recording of patients' health parameters, and the construction of customized CTD databases.

After data collection and before their sharing, CTD must be *anonymized*. Tools that can be used to anonymize CTD are, for example, [amnesia](#) and the R package [sdcMicro](#). Furthermore, if sharing would be limited by restricted consents, data repositories offer options of *access control*. Similar to the [CC Licenses](#) which are nowadays more and more common for research output, End-User Licences can be applied to safeguard or shield a subset of CTD. Besides access control, these licences can include agreements on not to attempt to re-identify individuals ([Towse et al., 2020](#)). Lastly, CTD preparation should ensure that the data that will be shared comply with the [FAIR](#) and [TRUST](#) (transparency, responsibility, user focus, sustainability and technology) data principles.

CTD preparation thus is a time-consuming task, requiring a set of technical skills which may be beyond the scope of clinical trial research projects. Due to time and budget availability constraints, preparation and sharing of CTD may become a low-priority task. These challenges address the necessity for experts in sharing of CTD ([Mansmann et al., 2023](#)). Research institutions may already have embedded CTD experts in research data stewardship initiatives. If you need support on CTD preparation, check if you have access to a local data stewardship network.

How to deposit Clinical Trial Data for sharing

Since several steps need to be taken to make CTD sharing possible, attention and strategy are required to save time and resources. It is important to keep your goal of CTD sharing in mind from the very start of your research project. Although, non-clinical research data can often be shared without restrictions,

CTD is restricted by ethical and legal conditions and can be shared only with the appropriate use of informed consent, anonymization, rights management, and access control (Towse et al., 2020). Various platforms, both general and field-specific, are available to streamline the dissemination procedure and the following subsection introduces two of these platforms.

- The Center for Global Clinical Research Data developed a global data-sharing and analytics platform, [Vivli](#), aimed at allowing researchers to share CTD. Vivli's focus is on sharing individual participant data (IPD) from CTD in favor of international research. The platform is a neutral intermediary among data contributors, data users, and the broader data-sharing community, facilitating seamless collaboration. Vivli offers citation and tracking of secondary analysis publications that are derived from the initial data, to incentivize researchers to share their data. Therefore, researchers are able to receive [CRediT](#) on their [ORCID](#) profiles. Additionally, researchers can track secondary citations from their data.

The Vivli platform offers [Study Submission Guidance and Support](#). In order to share CTD a researcher must create a personal account, submit basic information about their study, sign a Data Contribution Agreement, and upload anonymized data. Furthermore, uploading protocols, anonymized IPD, data dictionaries, and statistical analysis plans (SAPs) is recommended. Additional study elements such as an annotated case report forms (CRFs), clinical study reports, and analysis-ready datasets can also be included.

- [ECRIN MetaData Repository](#) Within the context of a Horizon2020 project, the European Clinical Research Infrastructure (ECRIN) has developed a clinical metadata repository (MDR). This is a database that links registered clinical studies together with a wide range of metadata, such as links to the original web pages hosting the study registration, the locations of results database entries or results summary files, information on related publications, protocols, data collection forms and any other available information. The MDR also contains links to studies' data sets, when available, or to the appropriate web pages that allow to submit data requests. The MDR is built on a foundation of over 800,000 clinical trial entries sourced from twenty-one national and international Clinical Trial Registries. While the original funding project concluded, the platform is supported by other EU-funded research projects, maintained regularly, and publicly accessible via a [web interface](#).
- Furthermore, there are many specialized data sharing platforms in clinical research available that can help you to share your data effectively. You can find these specialized platforms in your clinical research field, by having a look in the database of [Re3Data.org](#).

How to request shared Clinical Trial Data

Due to the sensitivity of clinical data, the access and use of the data often needs to be officially requested. Therefore, data requests often require a research proposal that includes:

1. What do you want to use the data for? (Research Question)
2. How are you going to analyse the data? (SAP)
3. How will the project be financed? (Funding)

Data sharing platforms offer information on their own requirements and templates for data requests.

- Besides data sharing, the Vivli platform offers the option for data requests, enabling access to data generated by other researchers. This requests, following the Vivli guidelines, should describe the process for how they make decisions about the use of their completed clinical trial data and should be as detailed and complete as possible. Vivli data requests include a research

question, SAP, funding and information on the team conducting the research. On the Vivli website, you will find [Data Request Guidance and Support](#) resources, including PDFs with tips and tricks, a form sample and instruction videos that will guide you through the data request.

- The [Clinical Research Data Sharing Alliance](#) (CRDSA) is a multi-stakeholder consortium established in 2021, comprising members of biopharmaceutical companies, nonprofit data sharing platforms, academic institutions, patient advocacy groups, and service and technology partners. A [data request](#) to the CRDSA can be submitted in a step-by-step online interface.
- The [Yoda \(Yale Open Data Access\)](#) initiative of Yale University facilitates open CTD sharing. YODA lists clinical trials on the website that are available for sharing with external investigators following approval of a research request. Data from trials that are not listed on the website can be requested, however, the request will necessitate more time to be fulfilled. On the [How to](#) page, you will find a step by step guidance for submitting your data request.
- [ClinicalStudyDataRequest.com](#) (CSDR) allows access to IPD from clinical studies with protection of patient privacy, confidentiality and an independent review of research proposals. Data requests can be done by submitting a proposal form including a research question and design, a data management plan, SAP, publication plan and information about the team conducting the research. You can find the proposal form on the CSDR [How it Works](#) website section.

How to use shared Clinical Trial Data

Data sharing platforms, like Vivli or CRDSA, usually do not ‘give’ you the data, but only allow you to access the data via their platform. This approach is an additional security measure put in place to further safeguard the privacy of the patients whose CTD is shared. These platforms generally grant access to proprietary and centralized analysis environments in which researchers can test their research questions on anonymized data. An exception to this is represented by the Yoda initiative, where data from some contributors might be transferred directly to researchers.

Therefore, while planning to reuse CTD, researchers should keep in mind the following:

- Data request processes can take time to be reviewed. Therefore, it is important to submit the data request sufficiently early. For Vivli, the review process takes on average 5.4 months and the range is 0.4-18.3 months. Factors that influence the timeline are the number of studies being requested, completeness of the request, requestors response time to questions from data contributors and whether the institution already has an existing Data Use Agreement (DUA).
- Access to the analysis environments may come at a cost (e.g., the Vivli analysis environment cost can range between \$12 and \$280 per day, depending on available computational power). You should make sure you have budget available to cover possible costs.
- The analysis environments may come with pre-installed software and not allow for custom software (packages) to be installed. You should therefore carefully consider if the available software will suffice for your analyses.
- Access to the data will be tied to publication of the performed analyses and consequent results on scientific (open-access) journals. Privacy restrictions might not allow researchers to export all the results generated within the analysis environments. It is crucial to assess these limitations and their impact on your publication plans well in time.

More about Clinical Trial Data Sharing

- Check our Primer on [Clinical research data sharing in Switzerland in a nutshell](#).

- The Center of Reproducible Science (CRS) is involved in international project on CTD sharing: SHARE-CTD is an European Union and Swiss Government funded project for four years and started January 2024. This doctoral network includes 11 PhD projects in 6 countries for masters in data science, biostatistics, computer sciences, medicine, clinical trials and clinical epidemiology. The overall aim of the project is to facilitate sharing and re-use of CTD to maximize impact of research. The [Share CTD website](#) shows more details about the individual projects.

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